

Studies on the Solubilising Action of Quaternary Ammonium Group on Certain Organic Reagents and their Metal Complexes

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The synthesis of certain organic reagents containing vic-dioxime, *N*-hydroxytriazene and hydroxyoxime groups have been described. The reagents under investigation contain a solubilising quaternary ammonium group $[-N(CH_3)_3Cl]$ and yield with certain metal ions soluble complex cations rather than the usual precipitate. Two general methods have been used for introducing such groups in the molecules of organic reagents. In one of the methods, the original reagent containing *tert*-amino group is allowed to react with methyl iodide, but in the second method the reagent is subjected to chloromethylation followed by reaction with trimethylamine. This property has been utilised in preparing colour reagents suitable for spectrophotometric analysis. The properties of the reagents are compared with the parent precipitants and it has been shown that just like the sulphonic acid group, the quaternary amino group also does not change the chelating properties of the organic reagents and the suitability of such group for solubilising metallo-organic complexes has been established.

Water solubility has been described as the most desirable characteristic of organic reagents used in inorganic analysis. In certain cases this characteristic has been achieved by the use of sulphonated derivatives of certain organic precipitant (Yoe, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **54**, 4139; Van Klooster, *ibid.*, 1921, **43**, 746). In general, such reagents are well suited for colorimetric analysis, because the introduction of such solubilising group yields water-soluble complex anion rather than the usual inner-complex precipitate with metal ions (Feigl, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 1289).

The acidic groups, such as $-SO_3H$, $-COOH$, and $-OH$ (phenolic), appear to have been employed so far to solubilise the organic reagents and their metal complexes (Ephraim, *Ber.*, 1930, **63**, 1928). It was considered worthwhile to ascertain the capability of the quaternary ammonium group in solubilising metallo-organic complexes. Such groups are widely used in the molecules of synthetic detergents to render them water soluble. Solubilising action of such polar group is also observed in the Girard reagent (Girard and Sanchulesc, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, **19**, 1095) which is used to convert high-molecular weight steroid ketones into water-extractable hydrazone derivatives.

In the present paper a general survey of the methods used for the preparation of certain organic reagents, containing such solubilising groups has been done and the characteristics of such compounds as analytical reagents have been compared with the parent precipitants. Although $-SO_3H$ group can be introduced into the molecules of organic reagents by a single process of sulphonation, the introduction of a quaternary ammonium group is not always easy. Two general methods have been used for the preparation of such compounds as are expected to have in their molecule groups, which are already known

to have chelate-forming properties with certain metal ions in addition to the solubilising groups.

In one of the methods, the starting compound already contained a tertiary amino group which was converted into the corresponding methiodide followed by reaction with freshly precipitated silver chloride, when the quaternary ammonium chloride was formed. The method is illustrated by the following examples involving the synthesis of a quaternary ammonium group containing vic-dioxime and a hydroxytriazene. As the primary object of the present investigation is to study the solubilising action of $-N(CH_3)_3Cl$ group, care has been taken to choose only those compounds of which the synthesis could be achieved easily by conventional and well-established methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 3-Phenyl-2,3-dioximino-propyltrimethylammonium Chloride.—This compound was prepared from already-known tert-aminoketone, β -dimethylaminopropiophenone hydrochloride, obtained by the Mannich reaction. The aminoketone (I) containing a $-CO-CH_2-$ group was converted into its isonitroso compound by reacting with calculated amount of butyl nitrite in ethanolic solution at $35-40^\circ$. The resulting diketone, monoxime (II), was converted into the dioxime (III) by refluxing with hydroxylamine sulphionate (1:1), previously neutralised with NaOH. On cooling the mixture, the dioxime separated, which was dried and allowed to stand with an excess of methyl iodide (1:3) for several hours, and the precipitated quaternary ammonium iodide (IV) was converted into the chloride by reacting with freshly precipitated silver chloride suspension in water. On evaporating the filtrate the final product (V) was obtained as a crystalline, water-soluble compound, decomposing at 166° . (Found: N, 15.46. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{22}O_2N_3Cl$: N, 15.29%).

In ammoniacal medium the reagent gave a bright scarlet colour with Ni salts.

Synthesis of p-(3-Hydroxy-3-phenyltriazeno)-phenyltrimethylammonium Chloride.—This compound was synthesised by following Bamberger's method (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2283), as modified by Sogani and Bhattacharya (*Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 29, 1616). Diazotised *p*-aminodimethylaniline(V) was coupled with hydroxylamine at $5-10^\circ$ with occasional addition of sodium acetate to prevent the solution from becoming too much acidic. The resulting 1-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazene (VI) was converted into corresponding meth iodide (VII) by allowing it to stand for several hours with methyl iodide and finally the chloride salt (VIII) was obtained by reacting with freshly precipitated silver chloride.

The product decomposed at 184°. (Found: N, 17.82. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_4\text{Cl}\cdot\text{N}$, 18.27%).

In this qualitative reaction the product resembles 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazeine. The limitations of the above methods were observed in the following cases:

(1) The original compound contains an additional heterocyclic tertiary nitrogen as in the case of 4-dimethylamino-8-quinolinol (IX) where the ring nitrogen preferentially undergoes quaternary ammonium salt formation and the resulting compound loses its chelating properties due to absence of a lone pair of electrons on the four-covalent N-atom

(2) In certain cases the tertiary amino group could not be introduced easily into the molecules of already-known organic reagents and hence the quaternary ammonium compound could not be prepared. In such cases the known organic reagent is preferably subjected to chloromethylation provided that the compound contains an aromatic ring and the chloromethyl compound is converted into a quaternary ammonium compound by reacting with trimethylamine. The following example illustrates the application of the second method.

Synthesis of 3-Formyl-4-hydroxyphenylmethyltrimethylammonium Chloride.—Salicylaldehyde as well as its oxime has been used as reagents for certain metal ions (Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Vol. I, p. 397; Vol. III, p. 259, D. Van. Nostrand Co., New York). Chloromethylation of salicylaldehyde was reported by Stoermer and Behn (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 2455). When 4-Chloromethylsalicylaldehyde (X) was allowed to react with anhydrous trimethylamine in ether, corresponding quaternary ammonium salt was formed.

The oxime of the aldehyde (XI) is a quaternary ammonium group-substituted derivative of the well-known reagent salicylaldoxime and unlike the parent reagent it gives only a coloured complex with Cu^{2+} , which can be represented as

Table I records comparative data of the three organic precipitants and the corresponding colour reagents.

TABLE I

		Solubility in water.	Reaction with specific metal ions.	Optimum pH range.	Solubilising group.
Vic. Dioxime	Dimethylglyoxime	Insoluble	Scarlet ppt. of Ni complex	9-12	Nil
	3-Phenyl-2, 3-di-oximino-propyltrimethylammonium chloride	Soluble	Soluble pink Ni^{2+} complex	7.5-10	+ $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^-$.
<i>N</i> -Hydroxytriazene	1,3-Diphenyl-3-hydroxytriazene	Insoluble	Yellowish ppt. of Pd^{2+} complex	2-4	Nil
	3-Hydroxy-1- β -sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazene	Soluble	Yellowish colour of soluble Pd^{2+} complex	2-4	$-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$.
	β -(3-Hydroxy-3-phenyltriazene)-phenyltrimethylammonium chloride	Do	Do	2-4	+ $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^-$.
Hydroxy-oxime	Salicylaldoxime	Insoluble	Greenish ppt. of Cu^{2+} complex	2.5-6	Nil
	2,3,4-Trihydroxyacetophenone oxime.	Soluble	Do	2-6	$-\text{OH}(\text{phenolic})$
	Oxime of 3-formyl-4-hydroxyphenylmethyltrimethylammonium chloride	Do	Greenish colour of soluble Cu^{2+} complex	2-6.5	+ $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Cl}^-$.